

Feasibility study of Eggitarian Baked Chips: An innovative healthy snack by LAB Solutions Co.

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Abstract

Snack chips are frequently referred to be “empty calories” while being a very popular and convenient food due to their high fat and sodium content. This study investigates the viability of providing Eggitarian Baked Chips, a healthier substitute for conventional fried snacks in selected areas of Cavite, Philippines, particularly in Barangays Alapan I-A, Imus City and Toolong II-B, Kawit. Market demand, supply conditions, technical operations, financial viability, and socioeconomic contributions are all assessed in this study. Slovin’s method was used to choose 395 respondents for a descriptive study design. The results show that 77.74% of respondents said they would be willing to buy the suggested product, and 98.45% of respondents are open to trying new food items. Demand forecasts reveal a significant disparity between supply and demand, suggesting a robust market opportunity. An anticipated first-year gross profit of more than ₱1,000,000 is revealed by financial analysis. Based on the study’s findings, the suggested enterprise has a good chance of being profitable and gaining market approval.

Keywords: *Snacks; Chips; Functional foods; Financial viability; Feasibility study.*

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Introduction

The desire for quick, ready-to-eat food items, growing urbanization, and shifting consumer lifestyles all contribute to the snack food industry’s continued explosive expansion on a local and worldwide scale. Snacking is still a big part of everyday eating patterns in the Philippines, especially for kids, teens, and working people. However, a lot of commercially accessible snack items, particularly chips, are usually heavy in fat, sodium, and refined carbohydrates, which adds to the rising public health issues of obesity, heart disease, and other diet-related disorders (Gibney et al., 2017; Lustig, 2020). As a result, there is little to no coordination and collaboration in nutrition-related activities between the health and other sectors in certain countries such as in Arabian countries (Musaiger et al., 2011). Such diets would typically contain harmful chemicals, including sodium, trans fat, and added sugar, which need to be further reduced through robust legislative measures (Mozaffarian, 2016). Even though food processing has improved human health, some of these achievements have resulted in foods that are harmful to health when consumed improperly or in excessively large amounts of a diet (Weaver et al., 2014). The World Health Organization advises consuming less sodium to lower blood pressure and reduce risks for coronary heart disease, stroke, and cardiovascular disease for adults and children with less than 2 g/day (WHO, 2012).

Consumer behavior has clearly shifted in favor of healthier food options in recent years. As consumers grow more health-conscious, they are looking for substitutes that offer nutritional advantages without sacrificing convenience or taste. Many people are actively looking for potential causes of digestive health issues and removing them from their diets (Nielsen, 2016). Food producers have been inspired by this tendency to innovate and create goods that appeal to health-conscious consumers, such as baked snacks,

low-carb foods, and protein-enriched substitutes (Lau et al., 2013). Even conservative customers who are resistant to new products and prefer stable values are a good target for differentiated marketing due to their comparatively higher consumption of specific functional foods (Szakály et al., 2012).

Using egg-based products is one promising strategy for creating healthier snacks. With important amino acids, vitamins, and minerals that promote general health, eggs are widely acknowledged as a high-quality source of protein (Réhault-Godbert et al., 2019). Eggs are a low-energy, high-nutrient food item that improves diet quality, especially when it comes to vitamin D and selenium intake (Ruxton et al., 2010). Because egg whites are high in protein and low in fat and carbs, they can be used to create healthy snack products. Because egg-derived goods, such as pasteurized liquid eggs and egg whites, must be refrigerated during the commercialization process, this could be particularly interesting for the inclusion of bioactive substances that must be kept at refrigeration temperatures (Miranda et al., 2015). Furthermore, the product's nutritional value is increased by adding nutrient-dense plants like broccoli and moringa, which are recognized for their high vitamin, mineral, and antioxidant content (Singh et al., 2018; Weber, 2017).

LAB Solutions Co. established a baked chips snack, by which the main ingredient would be fresh egg whites harvested by fellow farmers. Consumers, especially kids, usually buy unhealthy snacks that contain high percentage of carbs which is not good or healthy to their body. The researchers come up and invented the product "Eggitarian Baked Chips" to change the lifestyle of the consumers. It came from the words "Egg" and "Vegetarian" the researchers combine it as one since the product was inspired by organic. Through the demand of eggs, a new range of product for consumption can be cropped using them. The good thing about this product is that Eggitarian Baked Chips is baked, not fried and made from egg white. Meaning, there are no reasons to worry about gaining carbs when eating the said product because it's pure organic.

The main ingredients to make this product are egg whites, cheddar cheese, mozzarella cheese, broccoli, moringa leaves, and water. Spices are also optional but highly recommended. Eggitarian Baked Chips have many nutrients from its natural ingredients such as cholesterol-free, rich in protein, low-calorie, and contains essential vitamins from broccoli and moringa leaves.

Methodology

A descriptive research design was utilized to examine consumer behavior, preferences, and the feasibility of the suggested product. Structured questionnaires on food choices, snacking habits, price sensitivity, and readiness to evaluate and consume newly introduced products were used to collect primary data. Analysis of industry rivals, production and cost statistics, and market supply projections were examples of secondary data. The study employed frequency and percentage distribution, demand projection, supply growth rate analysis, cost-volume-profit analysis, and demand-supply gap analysis.

LAB Solutions Co. will be targeting people who need our product the most and are willing to pay for it. Based on observation, experience, and research, they are the following:

- a. Customer
 - Ages 6-60 years old, males and females who live in Cavite who values their health and wants to live a healthy lifestyle by changing their unhealthy snack choices.
 - They like eating snacks and trying new food.
 - Students, children, and workers who bring snacks to their schools and workplaces and parents who want to buy their children healthy snacks.
 - People who need to start changing their snack eating habits by replacing their old fried, unhealthy, greasy junk foods to our baked egg and vegetable chips.
 - People who likes to pack snacks during travel.

b. Respondents

The researchers conducted a survey to prove the potential Barangay Alapan I-A, Imus City and Toclong II-B, Kawit as its market. To determine the target market population, the proponents got the average number of households living within the area where the group decided to locate the stall of the business.

Table 1. Respondents

Barangay	Household Population	Survey Percentage
Alapan I-A	14,465	43%
Toclong I-B	19,238	57%
Total	33,703	100%

Using Slovin’s formula, the proponents estimated the average population of household living with the area, given the population of 33,703 with the confidence level of 95% (considering the error of tolerance). The resulting is a total of 395 respondents in selected areas of Cavite, Philippines.

Results and Discussion

Survey Analysis

Table 2. Survey Analysis (n=395)

Profile	Choices	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Age	12-17 y/o	166	42.03%	1
	18-25 y/o	128	32.41%	2
	26-33 y/o	69	17.47%	3
	34 y/o and above	32	8.10%	4
Salary	Student	159	40.36%	1
	5,000-10,000	140	35.17%	2
	11,000-15,000	55	14.01%	3
	16,000 & above	41	10.46%	4
Occupation	Student	256	64.89%	1
	Employee	116	29.30%	2
	Homemaker	23	5.81%	3

Table 2 shows that most of the respondents are around 12 to 17 years old with the highest frequency of 166, while the second to the highest is 18 to 25 years old with 128 and followed by 26 to 33 years old with 69. The least is 34 and above years old with the total frequency of 32. Majority of the respondents are students who are not yet working with the highest frequency of 159 and followed by people with 5,000 to 10,000 with 140 and behind that is 11,000 to 15,000 pesos with 55. While the least is 16,000 and above salary with 41. When it comes to occupation, most of the respondents are students with a total frequency of 256 and followed by employees with 116; the least are homemakers with 23. This signifies that the researchers’ respondents are not yet working.

In Table 3, which evaluates the survey questions, most of the respondents answered yes in trying new foods with a total frequency of 389 and followed by those who answered no which only has six (6) respondents. This proves that the respondents are eager to taste and to try new foods. It is a good thing for the researchers because the proposed product has potential in the market. In terms of having eaten baked chips, it shows that most of the respondents answered no with 347, while those who answered yes with 48. This verifies that Eggitarian Baked Chips will have a chance to make a spot in the market so that the consumers will also have opportunity to try and eat the said product.

Table 3. Survey Questions (n=395)

Questions	Choices	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1. Do you like trying new foods?	Yes	389	98.45%	1
	No	6	1.55%	2
2. Have you eaten baked chips before?	Yes	48	12.10%	2
	No	347	87.90%	1
3. What type of chips do you prefer?	Vegetables	190	48.05%	1
	Pork	61	15.45%	3
	Corn	41	10.46%	4
	Sea Foods	103	26.04%	2
4. What flavor of chips is your favorite?	Cheese	99	25.14%	1
	BBQ	52	13.10%	5
	Onion and Garlic	76	19.20%	3
	Plain Salted	28	7.05%	6
	Sour Cream	81	20.45%	2
	Spicy	59	15.06%	4
5. What factors do you consider when buying chips?	Nutrients	23	5.80%	4
	Taste	214	54.27%	1
	Price	81	20.48%	2
	Flavor	60	15.10%	3
	Packaging & Design	3	0.87%	6
	Brand	14	3.48%	5
6. How much do you normally spend on other chips?	6-9 pesos	246	62.33%	1
	20-29 pesos	80	20.14%	2
	10-19 pesos	46	11.64%	3
	30 & above	23	5.89%	4
7. What sauce do you prefer when eating chips?	Sour Cream	240	60.74%	1
	White Cheese	30	6.46%	4
	Sweet & Spicy	68	17.28%	2
	Mayo	57	14.52%	3
8. Will you buy the Eggitarian Baked Chips by any chance?	Yes	307	77.74%	1
	No	88	22.26%	2
9. How much are you willing to spend on baked egg white chips with moringa and broccoli?	10-19 pesos	212	53.64%	1
	20-29 pesos	139	35.10%	2
	30 pesos & above	44	11.26%	3
10. How important is it for you that you consume the correct number of calories per day?	I don't know	113	28.63%	2
	It is not at all important	28	7.14%	4
	It is moderately important	73	18.49%	3
	It is very important	181	45.74%	1
11. Do you consider yourself to eat healthily?	Yes	350	88.52%	1
	No	45	11.48%	2

Majority of the respondents chose vegetables as their preferred chips with 190. This is followed by sea foods with 103, while the pork with 61, and corn with 41. The researchers find it great because vegetable such as moringa leaves and broccoli is part of their product ingredients. Respondents chose cheese as they preferred flavor when eating chips with a total frequency of 99, followed by sour cream with 81, onion and garlic with 76 and followed by spicy flavor with 59. While the least is plain salted and have a frequency of 28. It is a good thing also for the researchers because the main flavors of their product are cheese and sour cream. Most of the respondents answered taste as their preferred factor when buying chips with 214, followed by price with 81; then flavor with 60; nutrients with 23; and lastly is packaging and design with 3. It gives the researchers motivation to make their product good as consumers want.

Most of the respondents spend 6-9 pesos when they are buying chips with a total frequency of 246, followed by 20 to 29 pesos with 80; 10 to 19 pesos with 46, while the least who answered for 30 pesos

and above with 23. The researchers plan to sell the product in cheapest price and might consider what respondents answered most which is 6-9 pesos. Meanwhile, most of the respondents preferred sour cream in their dipping sauce when eating chips with 240, followed by sweet and spicy flavor with 68 and mayonnaise with 57. The least is white cheese with the lowest frequency of 30. The researchers are happy to see the result because sour cream is the main dipping sauce of the product Eggitarian Baked Chips. Majority of the respondents are willing to buy the proposed product with 307, while those who answered no with 88. This proves that the product will be in demand in the market.

It signifies that most of the respondents are willing to spend 10-19 pesos on Eggitarian Baked Chips with 212, followed by 20 to 29 pesos with 139; while the least is 30 pesos and above with 44. The researchers plan to sell their product as cheapest as they can, so that the consumers can afford the chips. Most of the respondents considered that when consuming the number of calories per day, it is very important for them to know how many calories they are consuming when eating chips. Respondents have chosen very important with 181, while the least individual said it is not at all important with 28. Majority of the respondents consider themselves to eat healthily with 350. This shows that they are very conscious when it comes to their health when eating chips.

Demand

Table 4. Historical Household Population

Year	Population		Growth rate	Year
	Alapan I-A	Toclong II-B		
2016	14,370	19,100	33,470	0.0042
2017	14,420	19,190	33,610	0.0028
2018	14,465	19,238	33,703	
Total	43,225	57,528	100,783	0.0035

Table 4 reveals the historical household population. The total household population of Barangays Alapan I-A and Toclong II-B increased steadily but modestly between 2016 and 2018. The population grew at a rate of 0.0042 to reach 33,470 in 2016, with 14,370 from Alapan I-A and 19,100 from Toclong II-B. The population grew to 33,610 by 2017 (14,420 in Alapan I-A and 19,190 in Toclong II-B), however the growth rate decreased to 0.0028. The population increased to 33,703 in 2018, with 14,465 in Alapan I-A and 19,238 in Toclong II-B. Overall, there has been a steady increase over the last three years, with a total population of 100,783 and an average growth rate of roughly 0.0035.

Table 5. Projected Population (5 years)

Year	Household Population	Growth rate
2018	33,703	0.0035
2019	33,820	0.0035
2020	33,398	0.0035
2021	33,514	0.0035
2022	33,631	0.0035
2023	33,748	0.0035

In Table 5, the researchers projected the population of Barangays Alapan I-A and Toclong II-B for the next five years. The household population in the chosen areas exhibits little variations between 2018 and 2023, but it stays mostly steady with a steady growth rate of 0.0035. The population began at 33,703 in 2018, grew slightly to 33,820 in 2019, and then slightly decreased to 33,398 in 2020. It then steadily improved, hitting 33,514 in 2021, 33,631 in 2022, and 33,748 in 2023. The data shows a comparatively stable trend in household population over the course of the five years, with only minor fluctuations.

Table 6 showed the demand growth pattern for the next five years in order to determine the projected demand for the product. The expected number of consumers which is 33,703 has been computed by way of multiplying the total of household by market acceptability which is 77.74% and frequency agreement of 53.64%. Results will be multiplied by 4 weeks then will be multiplied by 12 months to get the annual year. The anticipated demand fluctuates slightly from 2018 and 2022, but it is generally consistent. It started at 674,594 in 2018, rose slightly to 676,936 in 2019, and then fell to 668,490 in 2020. Following the brief dip, the demand progressively increased, reaching 670,811 in 2021 and 673,153 in 2022.

Table 6. Projected Demand

Year	Projected Demand
2018	674,594
2019	676,936
2020	668,490
2021	670,811
2022	673,153

Formula: Projected Annual Demand = Population x Market Acceptability x Frequency Agreement x 4 x 12

Supply

The researchers used the supply analysis in order to know the responsiveness of the company in answering the demand market. In Table 7, according to historical supply data, from 2016 to 2018, all three brands—Jack ‘n Jill, Oishi, and Combos—saw steady growth, albeit at varying rates. Jack ‘n Jill saw the biggest growth, raising its supply from 12,500 to 19,000, with particularly robust growth in 2018 (35%), yielding the greatest average growth of the three. Oishi likewise shown consistent growth, going from 13,000 to 18,000, but with more gradual and steady rises over time. Combos, on the other hand, showed steady progress every year despite having the lowest initial supply and slower overall increase. The data indicates an increasing market demand, with Oishi and Combos following with more cautious but steady rises, and Jack ‘n Jill appearing as the most aggressive in scaling supplies.

Table 7. Historical Supply (3 years)

Year	Jack ‘n Jill		Oishi		Combos	
	Supply	Growth Rate	Supply	Growth Rate	Supply	Growth Rate
2016	12,500		13,000		11,000	
2017	14,000	0.12	16,000	0.15	12,000	0.09
2018	19,000	0.35	18,000	0.13	14,500	0.21
Average		0.47		0.28		0.3

2018 population: 33,703

Market acceptability: 77.74%

Frequency agreement: 53.64% Formula:

Projected Annual Demand = Population x Market Acceptability x Frequency Agreement x 4 x 12

Solution: 33703 x 77.74% x 53.64% x 4 x 12 Total projected demand: 674,594

The supply of Eggitarian Baked Chips in Table 8 showed a robust and continuous upward trend between 2018 and 2022, propelled by a steady 35% annual growth rate. The supply rises significantly every year, from 17,166 units in 2018 to 23,174 in 2019, 31,284 in 2020, 42,233 in 2021, and a peak of 57,015 in 2022. This trend indicates steady growth, strong and expanding demand, and efficient production capacity

scaling. Over the course of the five years, the data shows an aggressive and steady growth trajectory with no indications of decline or fluctuation, suggesting a robust and steadily expanding product supply.

Table 8. Projected Supply

Year	Supply	Growth rate
2018	17,166	0.35
2019	23,174	0.35
2020	31,284	0.35
2021	42,233	0.35
2022	57,015	0.35

Formula: Growth rate = Present-Past/Past Computation:

$$\text{Growth rate} = \frac{19,000 - 14,000}{14,000} \text{ Growth rate} = 0.47$$

Demand-Supply Analysis

Table 9 shows that the percentage of the share is determined by dividing the total supply by total demand of the current year. The demand-supply study for Eggitarian Baked Chips reveals a consistently wide disparity between supply and demand from 2018 to 2022, despite consistent improvements in manufacturing. From 17,166 in 2018 to 57,015 in 2022, supply rises dramatically every year, but demand stays high at over 670,000 units. As a result, there is a significant amount of unmet demand, and the gap only gradually closes over time, especially in 2021 when supply peaks in comparison to previous years. Nevertheless, supply still only meets a small portion of total demand, even at its peak. The predicted 14% market share, which ranges from roughly 88,000 to 92,000 units, regularly surpasses actual supply, demonstrating tremendous market potential and showing that the company has a lot of opportunity to grow in order to more effectively reach its goal share.

Table 9. Demand-Supply Analysis

Year	Demand	Supply	Demand-Supply Gap	Market Share (14%)
2018	674,594	17,166	657,428	92,040
2019	676,936	23,174	653,762	91,527
2020	668,490	31,284	637,206	89,208
2021	670,811	42,233	628,578	88,000
2022	673,153	57,015	658,372	92,172

Price Study

Table 10 shows the cost and pricing breakdown of Eggitarian Baked Chips. It demonstrates a systematic analysis of both variable and fixed costs, resulting in a strong profitability forecast. The low material cost per unit of ₱4.97 is produced by the total raw material cost of ₱993 for 200 packs. When direct labor per unit (₱1.75) is added, the total variable cost per pack is ₱6.72. A fixed cost per unit of ₱6.65 is obtained by dividing the entire monthly expenses of ₱38,329 over a manufacturing volume of 5,760 units. As a result, the anticipated total cost per unit is around ₱13.37. The contribution margin is ₱8.28 per unit, or a robust 54.80% margin ratio, with a target selling price of ₱15.00. Although maintaining or raising production volume will be necessary to completely maximize profitability, this shows that the product is priced profitably with a strong margin that can cover fixed costs and create income.

Table 10. Price Study

Raw Materials	
Water	10.00
Olive oil	95.00
Cheese	105.00
Broccoli	195.00
Moringa	12.00
Egg	576.00
Total Cost	993.00
Units Produced (packs)	200.00
Total Material per Cost	4.97
Direct Labor	10,080.00
Production Unit volume	5,760.00
Direct Labor in units	1.75
Total Variable Cost	6.72
Fixed Cost	
Rent	9,000.00
Utilities	4,249.00
Salaries	25,080.00
Total Fixed Cost (units)	38,329.00
Production	5,760.00
Total Fixed Cost (units)	6.65
Desired Selling Price	15.00
Less: Variable Cost	6.72
Total Contribution Margin (units)	8.28
Divided by desired selling price	54.80%

Listed below in Table 11 are raw materials together with their respective prices and quantities needed by the business to create Eggitarian Chips.

Table 11. Raw Materials Requirement

Item	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost	Supplier
Olive oil	Brushed to pan to easily remove the chips	Php 95.00 / 30 ml	30 ml *makes 100 packs	Php 95.00	R/L. Abad Supermarket, Imus, Cavite
Cheddar and mozzarella cheese	For flavor	Php 35.00 / 165 g	495 g *makes 50 packs	Php 105.00	R/L. Abad Supermarket, Imus, Cavite
Broccoli	Offers as much vitamin C as orange, and is a good source of beta-carotene	Php 195.00 / 500 g	500 g *makes 80 packs	Php 195.00	Imus Market, Imus, Cavite
Moringa	Very rich in antioxidants, protein, vitamin B6, vitamin C, iron, etc.	Php 12.00 / bundle	1 bundle *makes 80 packs	Php 12.00	Imus Market, Imus, Cavite
Egg whites	Reducing blood pressure to inducing weight loss; cholesterol-free; rich in low-fat protein; helps build muscles	Php 160.00 / tray	2 trays *makes 30 packs	Php 320.00	Imus Market, Imus, Cavite
Total:				Php 847.00	

Comparing the prices of rival cheese-flavored snack brands reveals a wide variety of price points that correspond to variations in perceived value, packaging size, and brand positioning. Budget-conscious customers are catered to by less expensive varieties such as Granny Goose Tortillos (₱6.00 for 25 g) and Jack ‘n Jill Magic Chips (₱5.45 for 30 g). For everyday snack customers, mid-range items like Leslie’s Baked Cheezy Puffs (₱24.48 for 55 g) and Oishi Potato Fries (₱11.85 for 50 g) offer more volume at a

reasonable price. Due to branding, packaging, and product distinction, Pringles (₱29.00 for 42 g) and Combos Cheddar Cheese Cracker (₱48.50 for 48.2 g) present themselves as premium snacks on the higher end. The market’s tiered pricing structure suggests that consumers have a variety of options based on their budget, and there are obvious chances for a new product to compete through improved value or affordability.

Table 12. Competitor Prices

Brand name	Unit	Price
Jack ‘n Jill Magic Chips Cheese Flavor	30 g	Php 5.45
Oishi Potato Fries Cheese	50 g	Php 11.85
Combos Cheddar Cheese Cracker	48.2 g	Php 48.50
Granny Goose Tortillos Cheese	25 g	Php 6.00
Leslie’s Baked Cheezy Puffs Cheddar Cheese	55 g	Php 24.48
Pringles Potato Crisps	42 g	Php 29.00

4P’s

Figure 1. 4P’s

PRICE: The price of the Eggitarian Baked Chips will be 10 to 15 pesos.

PLACE: As owners of LAB Solutions Co., the proponents want to start operating the business where they are most familiar with, which is within Cavite. LAB Solutions Co. will be located at Imus, Cavite. The researchers chose the said location because they believe the number of population and businesses established within the area has the possibility to fulfill the company needs.

PROMOTION: Promotion is a key element in putting across the benefits of a product to the customers. Promotion is the voice of the company which send out a brand’s message loud and clear to the audience. The more one promotes the brand, the more the customers will know about the product and the company; and the more they will be interested in the products. Because the company wants to reach the target market as much as possible, the business has come up with many different ways to promote the product.

The company sees this as one of the advantages in making more profit. The first step that the proponents take in order to get promotions started is choosing the best segment to target for a more effective

and less costly marketing efforts. The proponents tailored-fit all aspects of the brand and the product, to attract the market from packaging, label, to advertisements. We will utilize word-of-mouth and relationship marketing by speaking with friends, colleagues and relatives, and promoting the products to gather sales is perhaps the easiest and most obvious way to market the products. The partners will personally visit houses, malls and different locations in the area and outside to promote the products to prospects or potential customers as a form of field marketing/below the line marketing/local marketing. Prepare post and distribute marketing collaterals (flyers, pamphlets, brochures, posters, tarpaulins) and give them out to possible customers. The company will participate in different local events and put up themed booths on events such as the BSBA Business Expo, to turn passersby into customers. The business will provide free products during events and visits for the consumers to taste our product to encourage them to buy. Also, since the company understands the size of the market and the competition, LAB Solutions Co. will utilize different mediums or platforms to reach consumers from different parts of the world to gain awareness of traffic, publicity, and customers.

PROCESS: Chips are currently being offered by other companies or businesses on the market are commonly associated with the word "unhealthy" due to their carbohydrate, sodium and oil content, that's why the researchers came up with the low-carb Eggitarian baked chips with the idea of creating a healthier alternative to one of Filipinos' favorite snacks. The researchers are focused towards serving the consumers healthy and tasty snacks.

Produced Eggitarian chips will be distributed to consumers through the process below:

1. Prepare all the equipment, materials and ingredients needed
2. Preheat oven to 400 degrees (200 Celsius). Gently brush the silicone muffin pan with olive oil.
3. Whisk the egg whites, water and add herbs or spices.
4. Spoon egg white mixture just enough to cover the bottom of the muffin pan.
5. Sprinkle a pinch of cheddar and mozzarella cheese, finely-chopped broccoli and moringa on top of the egg mixture.
6. Bake for 10 minutes until the edges of the chips are a nice golden brown.
7. Remove from oven and use a small spatula to help remove the chip from the bottom of the muffin pan. Put the chips on the sides to cool off.
8. Put inside packaging.

Figure 2. Finished Product

Porter's 5 Forces

Bargaining Power of Suppliers (Low). The ingredients, materials, equipment's and suppliers are fairly simple. There are many suppliers available in the market that's why it is easy for our business to find the best one's that offer the best price, quality and quantity.

Bargaining Power of Buyers (Low). The products' prices are based on the costs of making them, therefore the prices are fixed. Customers cannot negotiate prices especially retail prices. However, bulk orders or wholesale orders may be negotiated.

Threats of New Entry (High). The business is in the food industry which is one of the biggest and fastest growing industries for businesses in the whole world. Food is everyone's staple product since it is a necessity. Humans consume food everyday that's why most businessmen could see this as an opportunity to start a new business related to food. There is a high threat of new competitors emerging because there are endless possibilities that people could innovate their products. Consumers taste change every day too, and they like looking for new food to try out.

Threat of Substitute (Low). The proponents created Eggitarian Baked Chips mainly to be the substitute to the common and less healthy fried potato and corn chips and snacks. These chips are made from ingredients that are unique and new to the local market, and the low carb feature it has makes it even more one of a kind. People may decide to buy their usual fried potato and corn chips, but the target market will always patronize the baked egg and vegetable chips.

Rivalry Among Competitors (High). Some consumers may not be as health conscious as the target market. People might continue to buy their old fried chips, or potato and corn chips. There are a lot of companies selling these products with a proven reputation and an established brand. These companies are also currently dominating the market. As a start-up company, the proponents will work harder in order to gain competitive advantage.

Socio-Economic Aspect

Contribution to the Government

LAB Solution Co. aims to be successful someday. In result, the company would be able to hire a lot of employee to help them in their needs, to help with the development of the government because they get taxes and to make the government a lot of projects and the company will benefit too and reduce unemployment in the country. Business is one of the major sources for economic growth, trading activity always help buyers and sellers, dealing in commodity, manufacturing activity, buying and selling help money to flow from one hand to another. For job opportunities, self-reliance always helps economy to grow in size.

Contribution to the Community

The business contributes to the community by producing and making available to the market a quality, tasty, affordable and healthy egg chips with tons of health benefits to satisfy consumers snack cravings without risking their health and weight condition. The proponents understand that the Filipino community has a desire for snacks with unique ingredients, and this gives the company a unique opportunity to make a very positive impact and contribution to the health of the communities we serve. Putting a product like this in the market will encourage people to be healthy and patronize locally made products and for other small businesses to innovate food products with unique and healthy ingredients. The opening of the business also means the opening of doors for people in the community to get good paying jobs. Having multiple small businesses like ours all striving to be unique, innovative, and better can result in a healthy marketplace and well-served consumers.

Contribution to the Clients

The proposed business product Eggitarian baked chips will bring satisfaction to customers who are looking for healthy and delicious snacks for a small price. The business is committed to promoting health among people by making quality and affordable snack available to all. We will contribute to retailers and other distributors of our product by helping them make profit by reselling them.

Contribution to the Industry

The proposed businesses will contribute to local economies by bringing growth and innovation to the community in which the business is established. LAB Solutions Co. will help stimulate economic growth by providing employment opportunities to people who may not be employed by larger corporations.

Contribution to the Environment

The proposed business will help the Environment by reducing paper waste. The LAB Solutions Co. will follow the paperless policy that most businesses nowadays rely. The company will encourage all staffs not to print email and draft documents and offering the ability to send documents to personal devices if that makes electronic review easier. In addition, the proposed business will provide indoor plants to its facilities that dramatically improve the aesthetics of the business. While in the process of growing, LAB Solutions Co. will implement projects and awareness every year to make environment better.

Conclusion

Based on the study conducted, the proponents have therefore concluded that the business is feasible and viable to the market. The newly introduced product offers a unique, new, tasty and healthier snack to the Filipino market. Also, basing on the analysis of our target market and our chosen location, there is a demand for the product the business is proposing. The financial aspect of the study further proved that the business is feasible because it was projected to be able to achieve its financial goals.

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